

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Pardayeva Mahliyo G'ayrat Qizi

ESSENTIAL PROBLEMATIC FACTORS OF USING AN ANIMALISTIC COMPONENT
OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN SPEECH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/APREL

★★★★★
HONORED
MENTION
★★★★★

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